

STRESS AND TIME DEPENDENT DAMAGE IN CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTICS

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Physical measurement techniques fail to show up any evolution of the material parameters of unidirectional cfrp loaded in the direction of the fibres either in creep or fatigue tests. Previous studies using the acoustic emission technique have revealed however that fibre breaks do continue to occur during such tests and may lead to delayed failure. Acoustic emission monitoring of the material during constant load and multiple level load tests offers the possibility of determining the time dependency of failure of cfrp. This study shows that the type of damage produced is independent of the details of the previous loading history so that the accumulated damage can be represented by the total number of emissions recorded. The load versus emission curves have been compared to the load versus damage curves of fibre bundles obeying a Weibull distribution. In this way it is shown how a minimum lifetime as a function of the load level may be calculated.

INTRODUCTION

The use of carbon fibre reinforced plastics in applications for which it is necessary to be able to guarantee a minimum lifetime is at present prevented, or at least limited, by our lack of understanding of the time dependent evolution of material properties. Extensometry and mechanical tests indicate that there is no evolution or modification of unidirectional cfrp loaded in the direction of the fibres although it is known that under creep or fatigue conditions the material sometimes fails (1). For those applications of composites in which the loading direction is known and is in an unvarying direction, such as in rotating machinery, unidirectional lay up is clearly the most desirable and efficient. It is however with this type of application where unforeseen failure can be most dangerous and for which it would be useful to have a better understanding of time dependent failure. The monitoring of acoustic emission originating at failure sites inside the material seems to be the technique which is most suited to achieving this goal.

Fuwa, Bunsell and Harris (2) have shown that the emission which can be detected from cfrp subjected to a number of different loading conditions is due to irreversible damage which is attributed to fibre failure. This present study has reconfirmed this observation on the material which has been examined, Fibredux 914 CTS obtained from Ciba Geigy. Some of the observations made by Fuwa and his colleagues can be summarised as follows.

1. During tensile loading acoustic emission increases in an exponential fashion however there are no emissions detected during unloading.

2. On reloading no emissions can be detected until a load is reached which is near the previous maximum load. See Figure 1. A figure of 94 % of the previous maximum load was given.

Fig. 1 : Acoustic emission recorded during cyclic loading of CFRP, after FUWA (3).

3. The same form of exponential acoustic emission curve as a function of load is obtained during the tensile loading of cured and uncured specimens, Figure 2. In the latter case the soft uncured matrix cannot cause acoustic emission so that in both types of specimen it is reasonable to conclude that it is fibre fracture which produces the emission.

Fig. 2 : Comparison of acoustic emission records of CFRP and semicured specimens under tensile loading, after FUWA (2).

Continuing along these lines acoustic emission has been monitored during the long term tensile loading of cfrp specimens.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The material used in this study was Fibredux 914 CTS from Ciba Geigy and obtained as prepreg having a nominal thickness of 0,125 mm. Following the procedure and specimen design described by Fuwa et al (3) thin unidirectional plates of cfrp were made with three layers of prepreg. The plates were cured in an autoclave for one hour at 170° C with a pressure of 0,7 MPa. Steel tabs were bonded on to each specimen which was cut from the plate. The adhesive was Narmco 329 and necessitated a post cure of two hours at 160° C.

All the acoustic emission tests were conducted with a 3000 series Dunegan-Endevco chain which consisted of a PZT-5 differential transducer, type 140 B with a dominant resonance frequency at 200 KHz, a preamplifier of 40 db with filters providing a gate of 100 to 300 KHz, an amplifier with adjustable gain and a detector transforming all peaks exceeding 1 V at the output into digital pulses. An envelope processor allowed all events which occurred within a period of 100 s to be grouped together. Emission counting could be either cumulative or as a rate by resetting to zero at regular intervals.

A logarithmic periodmeter has been developed which allows the logarithm of the time necessary to counting a given number of emissions $\ln(dt/dN)$ to be recorded as a function of the total number of emissions (N), with a precision of 10 % over seven decades without recalibration of the apparatus. This apparatus uses a digital logarithmic time base consisting of a series of pulses arriving at increasingly long intervals and an event counter.

The greater part of the tests which are presented here have been conducted with a gain of 83 dB although similar results have been found with gains between 80 and 90 dB.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

Constant load tests have been conducted at different load levels on a Mayes creep machine loaded by dead weights on a cantilevered arm pivoted to result in a load gain of 15.1. Certain specimens were subjected to various constant load levels in order to study the effect of increases or reduction of load.

Other tensile tests have been conducted on a Instron machine which had been modified so as to be controlled by the rate of acoustic emission which was maintained constant. In this way it was hoped to take the specimens very close to failure as the applied load was increased if the emissions rate fell and the specimen was partially unloaded if the rate increased. If the emission rate became very rapid with burst emissions the specimen was unloaded by about 10 % of the applied load at a speed of several centimetres per second. In this way the emission rate was maintained roughly constant for all of the test. Several tests at different steady load levels were conducted, using this apparatus is going from one load level to another.

RESULTS

The Effect of Time. Under constant load a unidirectional CFRP specimen continues to be a source of acoustic emission which shows that a mechanical degradation is occurring (4). Figure 3 shows a typical curve obtained.

Fig. 3 : Acoustic emission versus time curve obtained with an unidirectional CFRP specimen under constant load.

The acoustic emission progressively and regularly decreases, however a complete stabilisation of the material does not seem to occur although the rate of emission can be extremely low. The reproducible and regular acoustic emission curve may be expressed as a function of time, t , by an equation of the form :

$$N = A \ln \left(\frac{t + t_0}{t_0} \right) \tag{1}$$

where N is the total number of recorded emissions.

A is a constant for a given load but varies with the applied load level

t_0 is a time constant.

The value of t_0 depends on the origin ($N = 0, t = 0$) which is chosen. For previously untested specimens t_0 is typically between 10^{-4} and 10^{-3} s.

From equation 1 we obtain :

$$t = t_0 \exp \left(\frac{N}{A} \right) - t_0 \tag{2}$$

which when differentiated gives

$$\frac{dt}{dN} = \frac{t_0}{A} \exp \left(\frac{N}{A} \right) \tag{3}$$

so that $\ln \left(\frac{dt}{dN} \right) = \ln \left(\frac{t_0}{A} \right) + \frac{N}{A}$

The logarithmic periodometer allows us to record directly $\ln \left(\frac{dt}{dN} \right)$ versus N which as Figure 4 shows gives a straight line the gradient of which gives $1/A$.

Fig. 4 : Evolution of the acoustic activity versus accumulation of emissions in a constant load test.

The failure of these cfrp specimens was always very sudden usually without any warning by way of an acceleration of acoustic activity even in those tests in which the rate of loading was controlled by the rate of acoustic emission.

The Effect of Load Level. Any change in load level has an important effect on the acoustic activity. Figure 5 shows the two possible cases an increase and a decrease in steady load level which results respectively in an increase (aa') and a decrease (bb') of activity although by very different degrees.

Fig.5: Evolution of the acoustic activity in a test with several load levels. The continuous lines represent steady load conditions :

- | | | |
|-------------|-------------|------------|
| 1) 725 MPa | 2) 846 MPa | 3) 978 MPa |
| 4) 1040 MPa | 5) 1088 MPa | |

An overloading (cc') and then return to the original load results in additional emissions corresponding to an accelerated aging of the specimen. A reduction of load level produces greatly reduced acoustic emission activity which then increases on returning to the original load (dd'). In both cases, after a transition period of several hundred emissions a rate of emission is recorded which corresponds to an extrapolation of the original curve obtained at the applied load. The significance of this observation is that emissions recorded during overloading correspond to damage which would have occurred over a much greater length of time at the original load. A period of unloading almost arrests further damage which occurs at a very much lower rate than it would have done at the original load level. The total damage is almost independent of the load history of the specimen although the time taken to arrive at this level of damage does depend on the load history.

The same conclusion can be drawn from a series of constant load tests in which the specimen was taken successively from one steady load level to the next highest at a loading speed which was controlled so as to maintain the acoustic emission rate constant. See Figure 6. After a period of steady loading it was necessary to increase the applied load by a considerable amount to regain the initial emission rate. The necessary increase was such as to trace a general enveloping curve exactly similar to the curve which is obtained during a simple tensile test. A very similar result was obtained by Fuwa et al (5) with a cyclic loading pattern in which the maximum load at each cycle was maintained constant instead of a steady load being applied.

Fig. 6 : Stress versus total AE curve, with indication of acoustic activity in a test with multiple load levels. Continuous lines represent steady loads.

The experiments at constant load levels have been able to provide both the complete emission envelope curve and the values of A at different load levels, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 : Values of A recorded for two specimens.

1 st specimen		2 nd specimen	
σ (MPa)	A	σ (MPa)	A
942	150	1067	210
1096	290	1280	550
1256	610	1475	1260
1423	1640	1680	3530
1570	3070	1766	5000

In this way it was possible to define the parameter A as a function of the applied load by the following equation

$$A = \lambda \exp \left(K \frac{\sigma}{\sigma_R} \right) \quad (4)$$

where σ is the applied stress

σ is the tensile failure stress of the specimen

λ is a scale parameter

K is a factor which is independent of the amplitude, ie. efficiency of acoustic coupling with the transducer and calibration and is independent of the ultimate tensile strength of the material. The value of K has been found to fall between 7 and 8 for the specimens which have been tested in this series of experiments. If it is possible to determine a precise value for K for a given material by preliminary tests it becomes possible to predict the value of σ_R using the experimental procedure described above.

DISCUSSION

The experimental results confirm the hypothesis that with this type of specimen and loading pattern the fracture of fibres is the dominant source of acoustic emission. As the behaviour, and above all the failure of the material, are dominated by the fibres the acoustic emission which is recorded can be directly related to accumulating damage of the material.

The work of Rosen (6) and later Zweben (7) and Phoenix (8) considers a unidirectional composite as a chain of short fibre bundles with the length of each link being determined by the critical load transfer length δ . The matrix plays only a load transferring role and does not in itself contribute to the modulus or to the load bearing capability of the composite. See Figure 7.

Fig 7 : A mechanical model for the slaving rule in fibres and matrix, after ROSEN (6).

Taking this model we shall compare the load versus acoustic emission curve obtained for our unidirectional cfrp with the curve of the load which can be supported by a fibre bundle as a function of the number of broken fibres in that bundle, see Figures 2 and 8.

The fibres in a bundle break over a wide range of loads due to individual differences amongst the fibres and the distribution of defects on each fibre. The failure distribution as a function of applied load may be described by a Weibull distribution of the form (9).

$$\frac{N}{N_0} = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{f}{f_0}\right)^\beta\right) \quad (5)$$

where N is the number of broken fibres

N_0 is the total number of fibres in the bundle

f is the load applied to each fibre

f_0 is a constant

β is the shape parameter of the Weibull distribution.

The load which must be applied to each fibre to break a fraction N_0 of them is therefore given by

$$f = f_0 \left(\ln \frac{N_0}{N_0 - N} \right)^{1/\beta} \quad (6)$$

The load which can be supported by the bundle with N broken fibres is

$$P = (N_0 - N) f$$

so that from equation 6 $P = (N_0 - N) f_0 \left(\ln \frac{N_0}{N_0 - N} \right)^{1/\beta} \quad (7)$

Figure 8 represents the variation of P as a function of the fraction of broken fibres in the bundle using a value of 3 for the shape parameter β . The curve passes through a maximum which in an increasing load test is the ultimate strength of the bundle. Before reaching the breaking point however considerable numbers of fibres have inevitably been broken although where and when these breaks occur does not affect the final bundle strength. Increasing the value of β does not alter the

Fig. 8 : General shape of maximum load versus damage curve of a bundle with fibres obeying a Weibull distribution.

general form of the curve but reduces the critical fraction of fibres which needs to be broken to cause the bundle to fail.

The load versus acoustic emission curves for unidirectional cfrp specimens are very similar up to failure to the curve of load versus fibre breaks shown in Figure 8 for a fibre bundle although in the composite case the shape parameter has a value around 5.

The behaviour shown in Figure 8 is not time dependent if the fibres are elastic so that in applying it to the cfrp specimens it is necessary to add the possibility of delayed failures occurring.

Lifshitz and Rotem (10) have proposed a model which attempts to explain the accumulation of damage in terms of the viscoelastic nature of the matrix. This time dependent behaviour is most evident in tests on cross plied material (1). In terms of the fibre bundle chain model a flowing of the matrix results in an increase in load transfer length δ , possible interaction between previously isolated fibre breaks and the effect of a break being experienced over a longer length of neighbouring fibres, so an increase in the probability of their failure.

The results of the steady load tests at increasing load levels, as shown in Figure 6, show that the damage which occurs under steady conditions is an anticipated failure of progressively stronger fibres which would have broken at higher loads in a tensile test, Figure 9a. If it is assumed that fibres break independently of their individual strengths as in Figure 9b new fibre breaks and therefore acoustic emissions would be recorded with the smallest increase in load instead of the delay of greatly decreased activity which is observed.

Fig. 9 : Evolution of the load bearing capability of a bundle

- a) if the weakest fibres are broken first
- b) if the fibres are broken randomly, without consideration for their strengths. —

In order to study more closely the onset of final failure the servo system which controlled the applied load as a function of acoustic activity was used in an attempt to trace the curve of load versus residual strength, as shown in Figure 8. The assumption was that just before failure an acceleration of the acoustic emission would be discernable and that the servo system would progressively discharge the specimen and so trace out the curve. This approach was not successful as no acceleration of acoustic activity was recorded before failure except in a few cases in which bursts were recorded and partial unloading occurred as shown in Figure 10. Failure occurs in the composite specimen much more suddenly than for the fibre bundle and seemingly without acceleration of activity.

Fig. 10 : Stress versus total AE curve obtained for a CFRP specimen, with feed back control of the applied load.

This can be understood if it is remembered that the composite specimen must be considered as a chain of fibre bundles. The acoustic emission which is recorded as coming from a unidirectional cfrp specimen originates from points all over the material as has been shown by the acoustic emission location technique using two transducers. Near failure however one of the fibre bundle links is considered to attain its ultimate tensile strength and catastrophic failure of this link occurs whilst the rest of the specimen is still in a stable state, Figure 11.

Fig. 11 : Example of specimen fracture showing a localised crack normal to fibres.

As there are a great number of fibre bundle links in any specimen, the length of the link being determined by the critical fibre length ($< 2 \text{ mm}$), accelerated activity coming from one link will not make a significant change to the overall acoustic activity. In addition near to failure the damage which occurs probably ceases to be of general random nature and a concentration of breaks most likely occurs.

Minimum Life Time Prediction. Whilst it is not possible to obtain all of the load versus-damage curve it is clear that a specimen at its critical damage level N^* , corresponding to the maximum possible load, is able to support lower loads. As damage is independent of the load history the critical damage level N^* therefore corresponds to a guaranteed minimum failure level for all loads less than the ultimate tensile load level, Figure 12. The ultimate tensile strength can be determined by preliminary tests.

Fig. 12 : Minimum value N of the damage at failure, used to compute the minimum lifetime of a material under a given load.

The type of successive steady load tests on a given specimen, as shown in Figure 5, allows the value of N^* to be determined approximately, although the value of N^* must be in arbitrary units as it is not possible to relate this directly to a precise number of fibre breaks. The values of A at different load levels can similarly be determined as can K from equation 4.

Using these results it is possible to calculate approximately the lifetime of the specimen under different steady load conditions as it is equal to the time required for the damage level to attain N^* .

As we have seen the value of K does not vary greatly and the increase in damage with time for various load levels has been calculated for the specimen considered in Figure 5. The variation of lifetime as a function of load level is shown in Table 2.

σ/σ_R %	t_R (hours)
95	0.1
90	30
85	10 ⁵
80	10 ¹⁰
70	10 ³⁰
60	10 ⁷⁰

Table 2 : Minimum lifetime which can be computed from results of successive steady load level test.

As the prediction of lifetime only takes into account mechanical degradation and the lifetime rapidly becomes very long as the load is reduced it should be remembered that changes in the molecular structure by aging of the matrix have not been considered

CONCLUSIONS

The acoustic emission technique has proved useful in studying the mechanics and kinetics of degradation of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resin. Under steady loads greater than about 40 % of the ultimate tensile load damage has been observed to continue indefinitely although at a progressively decreasing rate which leads to near stabilisation of the material. The behaviour of the material and the acoustic activity recorded corresponds to a fibre bundle chain model and using the analogy of fibre bundle behaviour it is then possible to calculate minimum lifetimes for these cfrp specimens under constant loading.

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